

PRIORITY TASKS AND PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF EDUCATIONAL REFORMS AT A NEW STAGE OF SOCIETY'S DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: The article studies the theoretical and methodological foundations of the formation of an enlightened society in New Uzbekistan, the socio-philosophical aspects of the formation of an enlightened society in New Uzbekistan, the future tasks of the formation of enlightenment as a high moral value in New Uzbekistan. Also, the synergistic strategy of the formation of an enlightened society in New Uzbekistan is analyzed.

Key words: enlightened society, social laws, enlightenment, moral value, socio-philosophical analysis, synergistic strategy, dialectic, social development, enlightened reforms, stereotype, innovation mechanism.

Introduction. The social development of society is determined by the standard of living, welfare, lifestyle, and the economic stability of the state. Today, as Uzbekistan steps into a new phase of its development, significant changes are being implemented across all sectors based on the Action Strategy for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The educational tasks emphasize the importance of "...the development of science, education, and training, which is closely linked to our ability to compete globally," as stressed by the government. Therefore, the primary task is to reform the education system in Uzbekistan through improving people's living standards, ensuring adequate income, and creating new businesses and jobs. Changing people's knowledge, worldview, and mindset, as well as fostering a generation of skilled professionals, is also an integral part of this process. Indeed, education is seen as "the rational solution to solve the society's most pressing issues and a guarantee of youth development."

Literature review and methods. The issue of developing literacy in society has been extensively researched in historical and contemporary scientific literature by foreign authors. Specifically, the innovations in education systems in individual countries, the organizational structure of regional education, the role of higher education in societal development, the principles of enhancing its quality, the adoption of common educational programs in European educational systems, and the introduction of cultural concepts into education have been systematically studied. In Uzbekistan, the philosophical

aspects of social development, the liberalization of the education system, and the impact of development on economic or legal consciousness have been examined by philosophers, political scientists, economists, and sociologists.

Results and discussion. In the educational process, it is essential to communicate the main significance and necessity of the changes, focusing on achieving the support of the organization's innovative policies and overcoming the resistance to change from ordinary staff. These tasks align with the strategic management approaches that ensure the effectiveness of development strategies not only for company management but for the entire organization's workforce. As the development of modern science and advanced technologies becomes an essential condition for any state's progress, Uzbekistan has mobilized all its resources to ensure that the new generation is both physically and mentally well-developed. As a result, effective education and a high level of social prosperity must be formed.

In the new phase of Uzbekistan's development, the key demands and tasks for education can be grouped into several categories:

Firstly, in industrialized countries, the training of personnel is seen as a means of ensuring competitiveness and is based on a stable system of company-employee relations. In the 1950s, representatives of Japanese industrial management understood that the key asset of a company is its people. By the 1970s, developed countries had adopted the concept of continuous education, recognizing it as an effective solution to ensure the qualification of personnel in line with the dynamic demands of technical development. Every year, large Western corporations allocate 2-5 percent of their budgets for employee training and professional development. In the United States, educational spending exceeds \$200 billion, and in Canada, an average of \$500 is allocated per employee. For instance, according to Motorola, every dollar spent on education returns \$33 in profit. Such data can also be found in academic articles.

In Uzbekistan's new development phase, creating a prospective educational system, emphasizing quality and competitiveness in personnel training, and establishing the principles of legality, fairness, and transparency in management are critical factors for achieving social progress. According to Professor Sadulla Otamuratov's reflections on the development opportunities of less advanced countries in comparison to developed nations, several key points can be highlighted:

Firstly, the technological and scientific achievements introduced by developed countries are more affordable. This is because, in these countries, the

necessary funding for development at the level of current demands is often insufficient. Moreover, there is a need to form intellectuals who meet these demands. However, it is often more economical to purchase these intellectuals than to invest heavily in developing them.

Secondly, time is changing at an unprecedented rate, and, consequently, progress is accelerating, with countries leading the way in achieving high levels of development. This fact cannot be ignored, as time is ruthless, and there is no way to stop it. This forces countries on the path of development and nations living in less developed countries to race against time. Indeed, failing to account for the ongoing processes and the acceleration of development will result in negative consequences for citizens' lives in these countries, eventually leading to fragmentation. Therefore, Uzbekistan, as a developing nation, must race against time and urgently implement educational reforms to join the ranks of more developed countries in social development.

In general, all countries worldwide strive for development. Is there a measure of comparison between developed and underdeveloped nations? For some countries, development means the accumulation of wealth, while for others, it involves ensuring the well-being of people, creating conditions for freedom and social security within society, and providing favorable working conditions.

Modern researchers in the world have also proposed several theories about the factors that contribute to social development. For instance, Nobel laureate Amartya Sen, in his work *Development as Freedom*, argues that social development should not be viewed solely as an increase in material or economic well-being, but as a process of expanding human capital opportunities. Sen links the process of social development with increasing human freedom, emphasizing that creating broad choices for individuals is a crucial social demand.

At the current stage of societal development, the number of countries that have achieved social progress is quite substantial, and this indicator continues to rise year by year. According to statistics, in 1960, 36% of the world's population lacked even basic education. However, by the early third millennium, despite a twofold increase in the global population, the percentage of people with basic education had decreased by 25%.

In the 1970s, half of the adult population worldwide was illiterate. Today, the number of illiterate individuals has almost halved, indicating that education is now considered a priority.

In reality, quality education determines the development of a country, and

in a dialectical relationship, the country's educational quality also improves, with each one enhancing the other. Therefore, developing countries must pay special attention to education. "While economically developed countries lead in education level indices, African countries lag behind in this regard. In industrialized countries, only 1-2% of the population is illiterate. In these countries, an average of 32% of the working-age population (25-65 years) holds higher education degrees. In Canada, 43% of people hold higher education degrees, while in the U.S., it is 38%, and in Japan, it is 36%."

In the current context of Uzbekistan's modernization, the development of education is a crucial task that requires immediate attention and reform. For example, the involvement of the private sector in the preschool education system has increased, with the number of preschool institutions rising, and the coverage of children in kindergarten reaching 60%. By 2023, this is expected to increase to 75%. Additionally, in the past four years, the enrollment rate of graduates in higher education has sharply increased from 9% to 25%, and this figure is expected to grow annually.

Thus, "acquiring modern knowledge, becoming a true intellectual, and possessing high culture should become a lifelong necessity for all of us. In order to achieve progress, we must master digital knowledge and modern information technologies, which will provide us with the shortest path to advancement. Indeed, information technologies are deeply integrated into all fields today." Therefore, understanding that development is based on true intellectual growth has always been a fundamental pillar of social progress in any society.

The global community has highlighted one of the unresolved issues in the world's education sector: "...100 million school-age children are not attending school, and two-thirds of them are girls." It has been emphasized that in countries with rapid development, strong social management and quality education lie at the core, and large investments are being made in education and science. We can learn from the experience of countries such as Japan, European nations, the United States, Singapore, Taiwan (China), and others, where scientific discoveries have had a significant impact on their prosperity and development.

In the 19th century, the industrial revolution initiated massive reforms in the education system, but only three countries were able to implement these reforms successfully and developed rapidly. In contrast, many African countries, as well as the early medieval history of Europe and the later medieval periods of South and Central Asia, witnessed stagnation in their educational systems for

various reasons. During these periods, socio-economic development slowed, many values lost their significance, and the low living standards of certain segments of the population became evident. Therefore, it can be understood that throughout historical development, societies that prioritized education as the foundation for economic growth are those that advanced.

We recognize that the rapidly changing new models and paradigms in education modernization pose new and challenging questions that we must be prepared to address wisely. By doing so, it becomes possible to build a strong civil society and establish democratic governance. For this, education must be conducted in harmony with upbringing. "Today, in countries that have achieved high economic development, the fact that the prosperity of the people living there does not necessarily reflect true development is confirmed by the ongoing processes of moral impoverishment. These countries face threats due to various factors, one of which is the disconnection between education and upbringing, a concern acknowledged by many scholars, specialists, and even politicians in these countries. While focusing on specific areas of education has positively impacted their development, the disconnect between education and upbringing has led to moral impoverishment. These nations are now spending their economic achievements on fighting moral, social, and ethical degradation."

Conclusion: In Uzbekistan, there is a strong emphasis on integrating education and upbringing in the process of building a new society. Undoubtedly, in a country where education is separated from upbringing, social problems will continue to multiply. Therefore, finding rational ways to incorporate educational principles of upbringing remains a critical task. The scholar Y. Qoriyeva, in her analysis of the modernization of education in our republic, emphasized that the improvement of educational levels in the development of individuals is the cornerstone of social progress. We support the author's ideas, particularly concerning the correlation between graduates' employability and the quality of education. This is because employers typically identify a good specialist before hiring, and recruitment is their right. We believe that it is time to develop new methodologies for social partnerships regarding the quality and effectiveness of education. Quality education is a driving force for societal development, and through enhancing education, we can contribute to the progress of our society by improving social perspectives, ways of thinking, and increasing social activism.

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